
Implementation of Smart City Policy (Case Study in Klaten District)

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research is to find out how the implementation of E-Government, Masterplan Smart City, and the Smart City Program for public services in Klaten Regency. The research was carried out according to mixed quantitative research methods with qualitative research (Mixed quantitative and qualitative research methods). The population and sample selected in this study are the State Civil Apparatus and Stakeholders who are involved in the research variable activities that have been determined. The total population is 138 people and the sample after going through calculations using the Yamane and Isaac & Michael formulas is obtained by 104 people. The results showed that there were changes in the implementation of E-Government, the Smart City Masterplan, the Smart City Program and Public Services, in Klaten Regency as the impact of the implementation of e-government in Klaten Regency and there were desired and unwanted impacts, both positive and negative, from the implementation of e-Government. government in Klaten Regency

INTRODUCTION

The concept of a smart city is the integration of stakeholders in an area, including the government, the business world, and community groups and individuals in creating a service climate that is effective, efficient, fast, precise, close and supported by information technology. At the same time developing innovation from time to time

In Klaten Regency there are six quick wins or six dimensions of the smart city program namely Sakura (In-Network Population Administration Service System related to the smart governance dimension, Titip Bandaku Program related to the smart society dimension, Matur Doctor from the smart living dimension, River School from the smart environment dimension, The Podcast Program Talks Klaten Shines RSPD and Rolasan as a dimension of Smart Branding, and Klaten is fertile as a smart economy.

In Klaten Regency, the smart city program has been designed starting in 2019 and has received full support from the Klaten Regency Government as stated in Perbup 52/2020 concerning the Smart City Masterplan. The innovation program in implementing Klaten Smart City, namely:(1.) The Village Administration Management System or Smart from the Office of Population and Civil Registry represents the dimension of smart government.,(2.) The Doctor's Maturity Program from the Health Service represents the dimension of smart living.,(3.) The Employment and Industry Information System Program or Sikendi from the Office of Industry and Manpower represents the smart economy dimension.,(4.) The One Day Two News Program or Sariduta from the Information Communication Service represents smart branding.,(5.) The River School Program from the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) which represents the dimension of the smart environment.,(6.) The Archives Digitalku or Titip Bandaku Program from the Archives and Libraries Service represents the smart society dimension.

Klaten is one of the selected districts in the movement towards 100 Smart Cities in Indonesia which was initiated by the Ministry of Communication and Informatics. One form of Smart City development is the Klaten Smart City Application. The Klaten Smart City application is an Android-based device that can be downloaded via Google Play.

In the implementation of Smart City in Klaten Regency there are several problems/obstacles, namely as follows:

(1.) The availability of human resources at the Communication and Informatics Office is still lacking, this is evidenced by the presence of several vacant positions or employee needs, out of a total of 36 workload analyzes 25 are still filled, (2.) There are still several obstacles to the application and website of the Klaten Regency Government both from the user and service provider side. Such as the condition of the application being down so that it cannot be accessed which is affected by network conditions. However, this condition is always under the monitoring of the Ministry of Communication and Informatics, so immediate action is taken to correct it. (3.) There are no regulations governing smart cities. Initiation and implementation of smart cities in Indonesia do not yet have a legal basis. Even though a regulation is an important thing in the implementation of a policy that will be implemented which is used as a reference. In the absence of regulations governing smart cities, the basic concept of smart cities has not been fully understood by both the central and regional governments. The Klaten Regency Government also experienced the same thing, which is still guided by the smart city master plan in realizing the Smart City Klaten., (4.) Lack of Human Resources. To be able to realize the smart city concept, of course, the collaboration of several human resources in the Klaten Regency Communication and

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Information Service is needed. Where each employee has a different job desk. However, in terms of the need for civil servants in the Office of Communication and Informatics, there are still several vacant positions. Therefore, competent and qualified human resources are still needed in their fields.,(5.) Budget limitations. To realize the smart city concept, the Klaten Regency government must of course spend a sizable investment. In relation to technology, of course, it requires a budget that is not small, especially if you want quality. However, due to the Covid 19 pandemic, it has had an effect on reducing the budget to create a smart city.(6). Lack of coordination with other OPDs. In realizing Klaten smart city, it has to do with making public service applications. The Office of Communication and Information is in charge of providing servers and application programmers. It is hoped that each OPD will coordinate with Diskominfo in utilizing ICT infrastructure for the Klaten Regency Government, as well as regarding system development. Because there are still several OPDs that use service providers in the application development process.(7). Society is not ready. Community is an important component in regional development. In realizing the Klaten smart city, the role of the community is felt to be very good as actors in building smart cities, maintaining good public facilities and infrastructure, especially in relation to the application of technology-based public services. Application integration is an important factor in the implementation of various government programs that lead to the development of smart cities with the aim of shortening the flow of public services which are considered long and convoluted. However, this will be in vain if there are still many people who do not understand how to access it.,(8). There is a Covid 19 pandemic. The case of the Covid 19 virus has indeed not only shocked the Indonesian state, but almost all parts of the world have felt it. However, this virus has had such a big impact on aspects of life, including the Office of Communication and Informatics in creating the Klaten smart city. Several plans that had been set were hampered due to the prohibition on mass gathering in large numbers, such as technical training to improve the quality of human resources for the Communication and Informatics Service as well as the implementation of outreach to the public in order to provide knowledge about the smart city concept. besides that the existence of a pandemic has affected the reduction of the budget to deal with the virus so that it does not claim more and more victims.

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

2.1. E-Government

E-Government is a public service carried out by all government agencies that are optimally coordinated with one another using telematics technology. E-Government must be seen as a means not as an end. In order for the implementation of e-government to be carried out properly, it is necessary to pay attention to technical and non-technical factors that can affect success. In general, non-technical factors are more domain than technical factors, therefore an in-depth understanding of non-technical factors is needed when designing and implementing e-government. The implementation of e-government which is associated with efforts to meet the needs of all sectors of activity both in government and society requires patrons from leaders who can set an example and share commitment.

E-government is the use of technology by the government for various purposes. Tambouris et al [1] put forward three main characteristics of e-government based on their benefits. The first is to meet the public's need to obtain information, then deliver services so as to enable transactions of government goods and services via online and finally encourage public participation in the decision-making process. There are three classifications of e-government, namely between government and society (G2C-government to citizens), government and business enterprises (G2B-government to business enterprises) and inter-governmental relations (G2G-inter-agency relationship).

2.2. Smart City Masterplan

According to Klaten Regent Regulation No. 52 of 2020, the Klaten Regency Smart City Masterplan is a planning document that is used as a reference in the development and implementation of the Klaten Smart City policy for the 2020-2025 period.

Master plan goals, Planning is a process that defines the goals of the organization, create strategies used to achieve the goals of the organization, as well as develop plans for organizational work activities. Planning is an important process of all management functions because without planning the function of organizing, controlling and directing will not work. The Master Plan (master plan) is a plan that focuses on descriptions of an organization's corporate policies. The plan has long-term goals and has a very broad scope. Thus the objectives of the Klaten Regency Smart City master plan are: (1).As a basis for planning in the development of the Smart City of Klaten Regency. - As an initial basis which contains activities that will be carried out to support the Smart City of Klaten Regency. (2).As an initial reference for the implementation of activities related to the Smart City of Klaten Regency. (3) As a basis for selecting decisions and establishing policies in the development of Smart City in Klaten Regency. (4) As a guideline that maintains the implementation of the Klaten Regency Smart City development so that it does not bias and widen or conflict with the vision and mission of the Klaten Regency Smart City. (5) As a benchmark and indicator of the success of Smart City development

2,3, Smart City

According to Supangkat, (2020: 109)). That The design of a smart city or smart city is a design for the development of cities, especially cities that are developing. The growth of smart city design has different meanings from several parties. The meaning is

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not only on a single factor but has meaning and discussion from various perspectives that are used as a basis., The concept of a smart city can be understood by looking at and summarizing the exact characteristics of a smart city which tend to be general from several sources. Smart city is a city design with the use of technology to assist in everyday life. Some opinions state that the smart city design can answer the needs of today's society in terms of relief from life and health, but this smart city design is experiencing differences of opinion from experts and there is no general understanding and design that can be used by all cities in the world.

2.4. Public Service

Based on Law Number 25 of 2009 article one (1) Concerning Public Service provides the following definition of public service: "Public Service is an activity or series of activities in the framework of fulfilling service needs in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident for goods, services, and/or administrative services provided by public service providers".

3. METHODOLOGY

This research on evaluating the impact of E-Government on Public Services is a type of evaluation research using quantitative-qualitative methods (mixed methods). The research design used is a sequential explanatory design or a combination model research. Combination research with sequential explanatory design is research that combines quantitative and qualitative research methods sequentially, where in the first stage the research is carried out using quantitative methods and in the second stage it is carried out with qualitative methods (Cresswell, 2009: 209).

The population of this study includes 138 employees in the Klaten Regency Communication and Informatics Service (in 2022). The employee who will be the respondent is as follows:

Employees of the Klaten Regency Communication and Informatics Office are mostly based on education level groups, as follows: Masters/Masters Education, Bachelor's Education (Bachelor), and based on rank/group IV, Group III, and Group II

Sample, To facilitate the research process related to time constraints and cost efficiency, the number of population set is 138 people who have experience of more than 3 years. The method of determining the sample in this study is to use the purposive sampling method, which is a sampling technique with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2018; 124). The sample of this research was 104 people in the Klaten Regency Communication and Information Service

To calculate the sample in this study, the formula used by researchers in this sampling method is the Yamane and Isaac & Michael formula (Sugiyono, 2018; 78):

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Quanttative Model

To examine the influence of intervening variables, path analysis methods are used. Path analysis is an extension of regression analysis. Path analysis uses regression analysis to estimate the causal relationship between variables (causal model) that has been determined previously based on the theory. Path analysis alone cannot determine causal relationships and also cannot be used as a substitute for researchers to see causal relationships between variables.

The causal relationship between variables has been established with a model based on a theoretical basis. Based on the results of the analysis of hypothesis testing, the results of the research model are obtained as follows:

Figure
Diagram of Path Analyss X₁ X₂ to Z through Y

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Qualitative Model

the average value of E-Government (X1) with a strongly agree answer of .398.4 is classified as a good variable. Respondents agreed that the average score was 5.55 in the good group. E-Government variables were grouped as variables that had good criteria.

The average value of the Smart City Masterplan variable according to the answers of the respondents strongly agreed was 100.2 which was categorized as good. The average value according to the response answers agrees that the value is 1.8 which is categorized as good and . The Smart City Masterplan variable is in a good position.

The average value of the Smart City Program according to the respondents' answers strongly agree with a value of .100.2 is classified as a good variable.

the average value of Public Services according to the answers of respondents who strongly agree is 102.8, which is classified as a good variable. The average value according to the respondent's answer agrees with a value of 1.2 which is categorized as quite good Public Service Variables are grouped as variables that have good criteria

DISCUSSION

Based on the calculation results above, the result is that the greatest influence is on the influence of E-Government (X1) on Public Services (Z) through the Smart City Program (Y), while the smallest effect is on the influence of the Smart City Masterplan (X2) on Public Services (Z) through the Smart City Program (Y), so it can also be stated that the Smart City Program variable (Y) is an intervening variable that influences the effect of the independent variable E-Government (X1), Maserplan Smart City (X2) on the dependent variable Public Play (Z) Based on the results of qualitative data analysis, the following data are obtained: 1. Information in table 4.22 average value of E-Government (X1) with a strongly agree answer of .398.4 is classified as a good variable. Respondents agreed that the average score was 5.55 in the good group. E-Government variables were grouped as variables that had good criteria. 2. The average value of the Smart City Masterplan variable according to the answers of the respondents strongly agreed was 100.2 which was categorized as good. The average value according to the response answers agrees that the value is 1.8 which is categorized as good and . The Smart City Masterplan variable is in a good position. 3. Information in table 4.24 the average value of the Smart City Program according to the respondents' answers strongly agree with a value of .100.2 is classified as a good variable. 4. Information in table 4.25 the average value of Public Services according to the respondents' answers strongly agree at 102.8 is classified as a good variable. The average value according to the respondent's answer agrees with a value of 1.2 which is categorized as good enough

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion in Chapter IV, it can be concluded as follows:

1. There is a close relationship with the empirical description of the variables E-Government, Smart City Master Plan, Smart City Program and Public Services
2. There is a significant influence of E-Government on the Smart City Program in Klaten Regency
3. There is a significant influence of the Smart City Masterplan on the Smart City Program in Klaten Regency
4. There is an indirect influence of E-Government on the Smart City Program in Klaten Regency
5. There is an indirect influence of the Smart City Masterplan on the Smart City Program in Klaten Regency

The conclusions of the results of qualitative research in this study are as follows:

1. The average value of E-Government (X1) with a strongly agree answer of .398.4 is classified as a good variable. Respondents agreed that the average score was 5.55 in the good group. E-Government variables were grouped as variables that had good criteria.
2. The average value of the Smart City Masterplan variable according to the answers of the respondents strongly agreed was 100.2 which was categorized as good. The average value according to the response answers agrees that the value is 1.8 which is categorized as good and . The Smart City Masterplan variable is in a good position.
3. The average value of the Smart City Program according to the respondents' answers strongly agree with a value of .100.2 is classified as a good variable.
4. The average value of public services according to the answers of respondents who strongly agree is 102.8, which is classified as a good variable. The average value according to the respondent's answer agrees with a value of 1.2 which is categorized as quite good Public Service Variables are grouped as variables that have good criteria
5. There have been changes in the implementation of E-Government, the Smart City Masterplan, the Smart City Program and Public Services, in Klaten Regency as a result of the implementation of e-government in Klaten Regency
6. There are desired and unwanted impacts, both positive and negative, from the implementation of e-government in Klaten District

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